

Effective removal of Brilliant Green dye from aqueous solution by adsorption onto biopolymer supported silver nanoparticles beads

Jolly Pal and Manas Kanti Deb*

School of Studies in Chemistry, Pandit Ravishankar Shukla University, Raipur-492 010, Chhattisgarh, India

E-mail : debmanas@yahoo.com

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Abstract : The present study deals with the adsorption of Brilliant Green (BG), a cationic dye, on alginate stabilized silver nanoparticles beads. Silver nanoparticles were prepared by a simple green method. The microwave irradiation process was applied to the preparation of alginate stabilized silver nanoparticles. The alginate gel is as both reducing and stabilizing agent. The resulting silver nanoparticles were characterized by scanning electron microscope (SEM), UV-Vis spectroscopy and Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy. Batch studies were performed to evaluate the influences of various experimental parameters like initial concentration, contact time and initial pH on the removal of BG. Optimum conditions for BG removal were found to be solution of pH ~ 3 and equilibrium time ~ 40 min for the initial concentration range of 5–30 mg/L. The mathematical description of the biosorption equilibrium and isotherm constant were evaluated by Freundlich and Langmuir adsorption isotherm models. Equilibrium data fitted very well with both Freundlich and the Langmuir models. The pseudo first and second order kinetic models were also applied to the experimental data. The maximum sorption capacity of alginate stabilized silver nanoparticles for BG at 5 ppm test level was found to be 99% at room temperature.

Keywords : Brilliant Green, alginate beads, silver nanoparticles, adsorption, kinetics.

Introduction

The release of large quantity of dyes into water bodies by textile industries poses serious environmental problems due to persistent and recalcitrant nature of some of this dyes¹. Brilliant Green (BG) dye is used for the production of cover paper in the paper industry. About 0.8–1.0 kg of BG is consumed per tonne of paper produced. However, in humans, BG causes irritation to the gastrointestinal tract; symptoms include nausea, vomiting and diarrhea. It also causes irritation to the respiratory tract, leading to cough and shortness of breath².

The removal of dyes from coloured effluents, particularly from textile industries, is one of the major environmental concerns these days^{3,4}. Various techniques have been employed in the past for the removal of dyes from wastewater^{1,5}. Most of these conventional treatment techniques are rather expensive⁵. But adsorption process has been found to be more effective method for treating dye-containing effluents^{6,7}. The adsorption process provides an attractive alternative treatment, especially if the adsorbent is inexpensive and readily available. Adsorption is

considered a versatile technology for water and wastewater treatment because very high levels of contaminant removal can often be attained by using an appropriate adsorbent⁸. The attachment of the pollutant can be physical or chemical, the chemical and physical structures and the electrical charge of the adsorbent can significantly influence the interactions with the adsorbents and thus the effectiveness of pollutant removal. Adsorption processes are characterized by their kinetic and equilibrium isotherms⁹. Removal of many types of dyes and metals has been removed by using different adsorbents by adsorption technique^{10–16}. Several mathematical models have been proposed to describe the equilibrium isotherms of adsorption. Some of the most popular models include Langmuir, Freundlich, Redlich-Peterson and Sips¹⁷. Activated carbon is the most widely used adsorbent for this purpose because of its high capacity for adsorption of organic matter, but its use is limited due to its high initial and regeneration cost.

Nanoparticles of metals have been investigated extensively in recent years¹⁸ due to their novel material pro-

properties which differ greatly from the bulk substances¹⁹. Alginic acid, which forms the main constituent of brown algae is a well-known biopolymer and belongs to a polysaccharide family. Alginate has mild reducing ability and biocompatibility. It is a renewable bioresource and low-cost material. This made it ideal for "Green Chemistry" approaches.

The aim of the present work is to explore the possibility of utilizing alginate stabilized silver nanoparticles beads for the adsorptive removal of BG from aqueous solution. The effects of such factors as initial concentration, contact time and initial pH were investigated. Experimental equilibrium data were fitted to the Freundlich and Langmuir isotherm equations to determine the best-fit isotherm equation. The kinetics of BG adsorption onto alginate stabilized silver nanoparticles was analyzed by fitting various kinetic models.

Experimental

Preparation of adsorbent :

The sodium alginate (LOBA), silver nitrate (Merck) and calcium chloride (Qualigens) were used without further purification. All the solutions were made in triple distilled water. The biopolymer supported silver nanoparticles were prepared using a microwave irradiation method. To the preparation of silver nanoparticles supported with biopolymer, the following procedure was adopted. To obtain a homogenous reaction mixture, the reaction solution was prepared by dissolving 0.2 mol/L sodium alginate and 1.0×10^{-4} mol/L AgNO_3 using triple distilled water in a 50-ml pyrex flask. Then, the vial was placed on the turntable of the microwave oven and the mixture was irradiated at a power of 300 watt for the duration of 4 min. The reaction was allowed to occur intermittently to prevent an increase of pressure. After irradiation, the dilute colloidal solution with pale yellow colour was cooled to room temperature for its characterization. The beads were prepared by addition of above synthesised silver nanoparticles with the help of syringe into the solution of calcium chloride in small drops until the syringe became empty. The colour of the resulted beads was deep yellow. Presence of divalent Ca^{2+} ions causes gelation to form beads of spherical nature having the diameter of ~ 2 mm. Beads were filtered and washed several times with triple distilled water until the solution

was free from Cl^- ion. Finally, these alginate stabilized silver nanoparticles beads were stored in triple distilled water for further use.

Adsorbate :

The adsorbate BG dye (CI = 42040, chemical formula = $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{34}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4\text{S}$, FW = 482.62, nature = basic green 4) was supplied by s.d. Fine Chemicals, Mumbai, India. The structure of BG is illustrated in Fig. 1(a). An accurately weighed quantity of the dye was dissolved in triple distilled water to prepare a stock solution (1000 ppm). Experimental solutions of the desired concentrations were obtained by successive dilutions with triple distilled water.

Analytical measurements :

A Samsung CE2877 domestic microwave oven (850W), Samsung India Electronics Ltd., New Delhi, India was employed for irradiating solutions. The morphology of the alginate stabilized silver nanoparticles beads were characterized by Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) at the National Centre for Experimental Mineralogy and Petrology, Allahabad. Concentrations of BG were determined by finding out the absorbance at the characteristic wavelength using a double beam UV-Visible spectrophotometer (Perkin-Elmer 135). FTIR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer Infrared spectrophotometer.

Batch experiments :

Batch experiments were conducted using 100-ml conical flask to which 10 ml of BG containing waste water and adsorbent were added. These flasks were agitated in a room temperature and shaken at a constant speed to study the effect of important parameters like pH, initial dye concentration, and contact time. Samples were withdrawn at appropriate time intervals and these samples were centrifuged. Fig. 1(b) shows that the colour of adsorbent before and after adsorption. The supernatant was used for analysis of the residual dye concentration. The effect of pH on dye removal was studied over a pH range of 2–11. The pH was adjusted by addition of dilute aqueous solutions of HCl or NaOH. The kinetics of adsorption was determined by analyzing adsorptive uptake of the BG from the aqueous solution at different time intervals. The adsorption isotherm was found by agitating BG solution of different concentrations with the known amount of alginate stabilized silver nanoparticles till the equilibrium were achieved.

Fig. 1. (a) Molecular structure of BG. (b) Alginate stabilized silver nanoparticles beads before and after adsorption of BG.

Desorption of BG from adsorbent were carried out as follows : After adsorption experiments with BG under optimum conditions, the adsorbent were washed with 0.5 *N* amount of HNO₃ to remove adsorbed BG. The colour intensity of the dye desorbed was measured at 630 nm.

Percentage desorption =

$$\frac{\text{Amount of dye liberated by acid}}{\text{Amount of dye adsorbed on adsorbent}} \times 100$$

Results and discussion

Characterization of the alginate stabilized silver nanoparticles :

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) studies on alginate stabilized silver nanoparticles beads were performed to gain information about the particle morphologies. The alginate stabilized silver nanoparticles beads are mostly spherical and closely packed is shown in Fig. 2(a). The average size of silver nanoparticles is about 10 nm. Fig. 2(b) shows the FTIR spectra of alginate stabilized silver nanoparticles beads and BG loaded alginate stabilized silver nanoparticles beads. In the alginate stabilized silver nanoparticles beads the peaks appearing at ~1400 and ~1525 cm⁻¹ are due to the symmetric and antisymmetric

stretching vibrations of -COO⁻ respectively. The band at 1635 cm⁻¹ could be due to the intramolecular hydrogen bridges. The (COO⁻) band of silver calcium alginate was found at ~1385 cm⁻¹. The broad band in the range of 3450 cm⁻¹ for alginate stabilized silver nanoparticles is due to presence of -OH groups^{18,20}. After BG loading significant change in the FTIR spectrum is observed. Some new peaks appeared in the region of 2850, 1340 and 1520 cm⁻¹ that are due to the stretching vibrations of C-H, C-N and C=C respectively.

Effect of initial dye concentration :

The effect of initial dye concentration on the removal of BG by alginate stabilized silver nanoparticles beads is shown in Fig. 3(a). When the initial dye concentration increased from 5 to 30 mg/L, the percentage BG removal decreased from 99% to 87% with increase in initial dye concentration. This is probably due to that the high con-

Fig. 2. (a) SEM image of silver nanoparticles beads. (b) FTIR spectra of {a} alginate stabilized silver nanoparticles beads, {b} BG loaded alginate stabilized silver nanoparticles beads.

centrated dyes exceeded the loading limit of adsorbent.

Effect of contact time :

The effect of contact time on biosorption of BG by alginate stabilized silver nanoparticles beads at $C_0 = 5$ mg/L for biosorbent dosage 2.18 g was studied. A rapid biosorption of dye initiated in the first 5 min and thereafter, the rate of biosorption decreased gradually and reached equilibrium in about 40 min and around 99% of BG was removed, Fig. 3(b). This may be due to strong attractive forces between the dye molecules and the adsorbent. Fast diffusion on the external surface was followed by fast pore diffusion into the intra particle matrix to attain rapid equilibrium²¹. Further increase in contact time showed that there is no significant increase in the removal of BG by alginate stabilized silver nanoparticles beads, so further experiments were conducted for 40 min contact time only.

Effect of initial pH :

Fig. 3(c) shows the colour removal by alginate stabilized silver nanoparticles beads over a pH range of 2–11. The effect of pH was studied with blank solutions of $C_0 = 5$ mg/L having natural pH 3. The solution was kept for 40 min, after which the absorbance of the solution was determined at $\lambda_{630 \text{ nm}}$. It was found that the colour was stable at the natural pH 3. However, colour reduction increased as the pH was increased, with the maximum colour removal at pH 11. Colour removal due to pH change alone may be due to the structural changes being effected in the dye-molecules²². It can also be inferred from Fig. 3(c) that the color removal due to adsorption of dye on alginate stabilized silver nanoparticles beads is maximum and constant for pH greater than or equal to 3. Since 3 is the natural pH of the solution, therefore, further experiments were conducted without adjusting the pH.

Adsorption isotherms :

The experimental data obtained at room temperature were analyzed using the Freundlich and Langmuir isotherms. The adsorption isotherm constants were determined using linear regression. The isotherm constants (Freundlich : K_F , the adsorption capacity and n , the intensity; Langmuir : Q_0 , the adsorption capacity, b , the binding affinity constant and R_L , the separation factor) and correlation coefficients (R^2), based on the actual de-

Fig. 3. (a) Effect of initial concentration. (b) Effect of contact time. (c) Effect of pH on the removal of BG by alginate stabilized silver nanoparticles beads at room temperature.

viation between the experimental and predicted values, are given in Table 1.

For beneficial adsorption, the adsorption intensity (n) in the range 1–10 is required. The observed value 2.611 for n indicates that the biosorption process was favourable at room temperature (Table 1). Table 1 shows Q_0 and b values of 0.132 mg/g and 1.578 L/mg at room temperature, respectively. The R_L value shows the nature of the adsorption process to be unfavourable ($R_L > 1$), linear ($R_L = 1$), favourable ($0 < R_L < 1$), or irreversible ($R_L = 0$). As Table 1 show, R_L values obtained at room

Table 1. Freundlich and Langmuir isotherm constants of BG adsorption on alginate stabilized silver nanoparticles beads

Freundlich constants			Langmuir constants			
K_F (mg/g)	n	R^2	Q_0 (mg/g)	b (L/mg)	R^2	R_L
14 1579	2 611	0 998	0 132	1 578	0 965	0 112

K_F = Adsorption capacity, n = adsorption intensity, R^2 = correlation coefficients, Q_0 = maximum adsorption capacity of the dye (forming a monolayer) per unit weight of adsorbent (mg/g), b = constant related to the affinity of the binding sites (L/mg), R_L = nature of the adsorption process

temperature was in the range 0–1, indicating that the experimental conditions in this work were favourable for the adsorption process²³.

Comparison of the two isotherms :

Table 1 shows the Q_0 and b values for the Langmuir isotherm, the K_F and n values for the Freundlich isotherm, and also R^2 values obtained from the linear regression equation between the values of C_e/Q_e and C_e , $\ln Q_e$ and $\ln C_e$ respectively. Comparing the R^2 values obtained from the two models, it was found that the isotherm was closer to the Freundlich model than the Langmuir models at room temperature. Comparison of the experimental equilibrium data with the theoretical equilibrium data obtained from Freundlich and Langmuir adsorption isotherms is shown in Figs. 4(a) and 4(b).

Adsorption kinetics :

Percentage removal of BG at a fixed adsorbent dose was monitored with time. The kinetics of BG removal by alginate stabilized silver nanoparticles beads indicated rapid binding of BG to the sorbent during first few min, followed by a slow increase until a state of equilibrium was reached in 40 min. No change in the uptake capacity was observed with further increase in equilibration time up to 50 min. The initial rapid phase may be due to increased number of vacant sites available at the initial stage. As a result, there was an increased concentration gradient between adsorbate in solution and adsorbate on the adsorbent²⁴. Generally, when adsorption involves a surface reaction process, the initial adsorption is rapid. Then, a slower adsorption would follow as the available adsorption site gradually decreases. Kinetics²⁵ of sorption was modelled by the pseudo-first order equation and the pseudo-second order equation²⁶ models at 5 mg/L initial concentration. Figs. 5(a) and 5(b) show plots of pseudo-

Fig. 4. (a) Freundlich isotherm plots (b) Langmuir isotherm plots for adsorption of BG on alginate stabilized silver nanoparticles beads at room temperature

first order equilibrium and pseudo-second order equilibrium, respectively. The adsorption kinetic data fitted best in pseudo-second order model, where a linear plot of T vs Q_t was obtained. The correlation coefficients and the rate constants for BG are summarized in Table 2. These results suggest that adsorption is not diffusion controlled but is chemisorptions

Desorption studies :

Desorption studies help to elucidate the nature of adsorption and recycling of the spent adsorbent and the dye. To make the sorbent economically competitive, the prepared composite material should be reused for ‘ n ’ number of cycles. A 99% of the BG was removed in the first cycle. The used adsorbent was treated with 0.5 HNO_3

Table 2. Adsorption kinetics data for removal of BG by alginate stabilized silver nanoparticles beads at room temperature

Sl no	Parameters	Adsorbent value
1	Pseudo-first order model	
	K_1	0 005
	R^2	0 948
2	Pseudo-second order model	
	K_2	1829 5
	R^2	0 998

K_1 = Pseudo-first order rate constant, K_2 = pseudo-second order rate constant, R^2 = correlation coefficient

Fig. 5. (a) Pseudo-first-order kinetic plots. (b) Pseudo-second order kinetic plots for the removal of BG.

which resulted in to 99% stripping of BG. The adsorption ability was almost completely resumed after the regeneration of acid-treated sorbent. In the second cycle the material could now remove 97% BG that could be desorbed up to 98%. In the third cycle 94% adsorption and 96% desorption was possible. The removal decreased nominally per cycle up to 20 cycles suggesting high efficiency of the adsorbent. In the last cycle 70% adsorption and 82% desorption was feasible. Thus, it may be considered that a good desorption performance of adsorbents is useful in the recovery of the removed dyes. This, again, adds to the economic viability of the system.

Conclusions :

This study showed that alginate stabilized silver nanoparticles beads were an effective sorbent for removal of BG dye from aqueous solution. The adsorption of BG on alginate stabilized silver nanoparticles beads are explained well by the Langmuir and Freundlich isotherm models. The sorption capacities were found to be 99% BG of alginate stabilized silver nanoparticles. The sorption equilibriums were reached at about 40 min. Experiments were performed as a function of initial concentration, contact time and initial pH. Adsorption kinetics followed the pseudo-second order equation, which suggested that chemisorptions significantly contributed to the adsorption process. Overall, alginate stabilized silver nanoparticles showed excellent adsorptive characteristics for the removal of BG from aqueous solution.

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